

Intercultural Competence and Youth Leadership Development in Lagos State

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Abstract

Lagos State is home and habitat to people across cultural backgrounds and nationalities in the world. Several factors such as location, business opportunities, commerce and industries are responsible for accommodation of different cultural groups and individuals within and outside Nigeria. The impact of cultural diversity is evident in so many areas in the state. For instance, non-Lagosians are also actively involved in governance and administration in Lagos State. People from other cultural backgrounds are recognised, they can vie for political offices and be voted for. Thus, leadership in Lagos State requires intercultural competence for efficient performance and effective service delivery. As a result, this study examined Lagos State youth's level of exposure and awareness about intercultural competence through a structured questionnaire. The researchers examined the conceptual understanding of intercultural competence developed by some scholars, and equally adopted the Process Model of Intercultural Competence as a theoretical framework for the study. Among several recommendations of this study is that the Lagos State government and youth-focused organisations should review their leadership development schemes, include intercultural competence and explore intercultural leadership approach in their leadership development initiatives.

Keywords: Intercultural Competence, Leadership Development, Youth Leadership, Lagos State

Introduction

In recent times, nearly every discipline or field of study treads the path of intercultural relation and communication competence because humankind is largely relational. Much more specifically, the current trend of globalization requires intercultural competence for leadership effectiveness, service delivery and performance. It would take an intercultural competent person to lead or work efficiently and effectively in this era of globalisation where the nations of the world depend on each other for

survival and sustainable development. In the case of Lagos, several factors such as location, business opportunities, commerce and industries are responsible for the accommodation of different cultural groups and individuals within and outside Nigeria. Intercultural competence is a necessity for leaders, leadership performance and service delivery in Lagos State, and in a country like Nigeria formed by an amalgamation of different ethnic and cultural backgrounds.

Conceptual Clarifications and Literature Review

Intercultural Competence

Is a global trend in the academic discipline because of the cross cultural relationship, diplomacy and political relationship, economy and transaction across the world. Given this, Shashini (2015) conceptualised intercultural competence as the ability to communicate successfully with culturally different people using one's intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes. It is a working tool in a culturally diverse society and working environment. According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO, 2013), intercultural competence involves the knowledge and understanding of one's culture, other cultures, specific culture, general culture, sociolinguistic awareness, cultural adaptation process, ethnocentrism, ethno-relativism, culture shock, and reverse culture shock. Consequently, a scholar conceptualised intercultural competence as a complex of abilities needed to perform effectively and appropriately when interacting with others who are linguistically and culturally different from oneself (Fantini 2021). Intercultural competence enables one to have a good command of language and the right choice of words when dealing with people from different cultural background. For instance, the Lagos State working environment demands leadership at all levels to possess intercultural competence to perform effectively and appropriately.

In addition, Joseph & Christopher (2012) argued that most of the researches conducted on intercultural competence primarily used research instruments such as individual self report, surveys, or open-ended interviews to achieve this purpose, and the area of assessment focuses on individuals' attitudes, personalities, values, and motives. Through research findings, Marina & Irina (2021) considered the following as components of intercultural competence, world knowledge, foreign language proficiency, cultural empathy, approval of foreign people and cultures, and ability to practice one's profession in an international setting. With this description, intercultural competence has some components which encompass individual knowledge of cultural diversities, skills, attitudes and communication competence.

Leadership Development

Youth development is fundamental and a foundation for the future of any society and organisation in the world. As a result, scholar like De Beer (2020) stressed that the need to develop leadership has been evolving in response to the internal and external pressures confronting organizations. Supporting this, Peter (2018) emphasised that the ability to see the future and anticipate the consequence of decisions

made now will require people to go beyond simply relying on past experience. Leadership development essential focuses on looking ahead and preparing for a new experience.

In addition, Sofia et al. (2021) argued that leadership development is the starting point for organizational leadership in terms of developing the organization to address its strategic challenges, reach its goals, and visions. It is important to note that leadership development is not limited to the organisation's progress. Carroll (2019) added that leadership development primarily focuses on individual leader's growth, and how they need to be effective to improve their performance.

Youths in their attitude and behaviour and in the course of day-to-day work demonstrate the commitment and potential to take on leadership roles and responsibilities (Emerging Leader's Framework, 2019). This suggests that leadership development is a function of training individual leaders and developing their skills and competencies (Servane et al., 2019). Leadership development in this perspective focuses on grooming and developing emerging leaders for leadership roles in an organisation or nation.

Youth Leadership Development in Lagos State

Globally, the quest for a new generation of leaders and those who will exercise uncommon leadership qualities has become a serious concern. As a result, more leadership training institutions are opening across the globe. A group of scholars describes leadership development as an expansion of a person's capability to be effective in a leadership role and process (Van Velsor, McCauley & Ruderman, 2010). Literarily, this concept seems to promote self growth and development. In light of this, since 1999 when Nigeria returned to democratic leadership and governance, Lagos State has the narrative of youth leadership development initiatives over the years. History has it that successful governors of Lagos State have had different leadership development initiative programs and training over the years. Each of them understands the necessity of youth development and adopted diverse approaches relevant to their vision and administration.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is undergirded by the Process Model of Intercultural Competence. The theory is equally proposed based on the working definition of intercultural competence, which is “the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on one's intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes”(Tennekoon, 2015). The theory focuses on the essential components of intercultural competence such as attitudes, knowledge and skills, and how to develop them (Deardoff, 2009). The theory provides variables and components for the assessment of intercultural competence in leadership development among youths in Lagos State. It gives insight into the basis and progressive means of acquiring intercultural competence. More importantly, it describes intercultural competence as a lifetime skill that requires continuous learning as a person lives or engages in an intercultural assignment. The theory is explicit on required components for leadership development among youths, the dimension of learning, and a template for development of intercultural competence at any level.

Methodology

The primary data was largely generated through a field survey using a structured questionnaire to investigate issues from different perspectives and ascertain the originality of the study. The questionnaire contained both open and closed ended questions designed in such a way that the respondents were able to identify their level of awareness about intercultural competence. The study engaged 306 youths, both leaders and members of the selected youth-focused organisations in Lagos State. The selected organisations are Royal Ambassadors of Nigeria, Anti-Social Vices Club, Lydias Auxiliary, Lagos Community Youth Development Initiatives and Lagos State Chapter of Coalition of Nigerian Youth on Security and Safety Affairs. All the selected youth organisations include boys and girls, except Royal Ambassadors which comprises only young boys while the Lydia Auxiliary comprises only young girls. The study adopted a purposive stratified random sampling method to select a specified number of respondents from different youth organisations.

Assessment of Youth Awareness about Intercultural Competence in Lagos State

This section of the study seeks to determine the level of awareness of youth residing in Lagos State about intercultural competence. To enable the researcher to determine the level of youth awareness of intercultural competence, five questions were further formulated as follows:

- i. Do you consider intercultural competence to be the recognition of one's culture and the ability to relate with other cultures acceptably?
- ii. Is intercultural competence the knowledge of cultures that are superior among a group of cultures?
- iii. Do you consider intercultural competence to be the ability to think, communicate, and act effectively and appropriately among people from different cultures?
- iv. To what extent do you agree that intercultural competence is a skill needed to promote one's culture excellently among other cultures in any situation?
- v. To what extent do you agree that intercultural competence enhances flexibility, openness, listening, observing, interpreting, and seeing different values in other cultures?

All 306 participants responded to the above questions. A summary of the responses of the participants is shown in the table below

Table 1: A Summary of responses on Youth Awareness about Intercultural Competence in Lagos State

<i>Description</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neither Agree nor Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
Intercultural competence is the recognition of one's culture and ability to relate with other cultures in an acceptable way	152	146	4	2	2
Intercultural competence is the knowledge of cultures that are superior among a group of cultures	33	92	36	112	33
Intercultural competence is the ability to think, communicate, and act effectively and appropriately among people from different cultures	162	132	10	2	
Intercultural competence is a skill needed to promote one's culture excellently among other cultures in any situation.	95	138	28	39	6
Intercultural competence enhances flexibility, openness listening, observing, interpreting, and seeing different values in other cultures.	158	139	6	2	1

Source: Field Work, 2022

The response pattern of the respondents was similar to sub-questions (i), (iii) and (v). In this instance, it was determined through the following parameters: that strongly agree > agree > neither agree nor disagree > disagree > strongly disagree. In effect, over 90% of the respondents at least agreed with the assertion stated in the questionnaire. The trend graph of the respondents is shown in the figure below:

Figure 1: Response pattern of participants on sub-questions (i), (iii) and (iv)

The researcher inversed sub-questions (ii) and (iv), to prevent response bias. The outcome of the responses of the participants is presented in the graph above.

Figure 2: Intercultural competence is knowledge of cultures that are superior among a group of cultures

Based on the above chart, it can be observed that the responses are polarized, unlike the response observed in (i), (iii), and (v) sub-questions. “Agree” and “Disagree” responses accounted for the

highest frequency with 30% and 37%, respectively. “Strongly agree”, “Neither disagree nor agree” and “Strongly Agree” accounted for 11% of each of the responses.

Despite being inversed, an analysis of sub-questions (iv) shows that at most, 76% of the respondents agreed that, “Intercultural competence is a skill needed to promote one's culture excellently among other cultures in any situation,” while at most, 15% disagreed with the statement. The responses of the participants are represented in the figure below:

Figure 3: Intercultural competence is a skill needed to promote one's culture excellently among other cultures in any situation.

The researcher further analyzed the participants' responses by determining the weights of each response and corresponding scores. Sub-questions (ii) and (iv) are inverse questions, so weights from 1 to 5 were assigned from strongly agree to strongly disagree respectively, while sub-question (i), (iii), and (v) were assigned normal weights from 5 to 1, representing strongly agree to strongly disagree, respectively.

The descriptive statistics information of the participants is shown in the table below

Table 2 : Descriptive Statistics on Youth Awareness about Intercultural Competence in Lagos State

<i>Description</i>	<i>Highly Aware</i>	<i>Aware</i>	<i>Neither Aware nor Unaware</i>	<i>Unaware</i>	<i>Highly Unaware</i>
Mean	511	454.4	50.4	94.4	26.2
Median	760	528	30	4	2
Standard Deviation	380.89	174.37	42.97	127.99	40.89
Kurtosis	-2.91	3.29	-2.23	-1.7	2.57
Skewness	-0.67	-1.8	0.68	0.89	1.69
Range	780	428	96	272	95
Count	5	5	5	5	5

Confidence Level= 95.0%

Source: Field Work, 2022

The mean scores of the awareness level of participants were higher than the mean score of participants that were unaware of intercultural competence. Specifically, the highest mean score of 511 was recorded for “Highly Aware” whilst the least mean score of 26.20 was recorded for “highly unaware.” The data was also tested for skewness and kurtosis to determine the normal univariate distribution. The coefficient of skewness ranged from -1.80 to 1.69, whilst the kurtosis level ranged from -2.91 to 3.29. All the data were analysed at a 95% confidence level.

Findings and Discussion

From the analysis of the findings, over 90% of the respondents displayed knowledge of awareness of intercultural competence as stated in the questionnaire. Though awareness of intercultural competence is high among the youths, but there is a seemingly challenge of in-depth understanding among a few respondents (in sub questions (ii) and (iv)). The respondents' opinions are contrary to the conceptual understanding of intercultural competence among scholars and the theoretical frameworks that this study rests upon. The respondents are also in sharp contrast to the global concept of intercultural competence.

For instance, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation in its research publication emphatically stressed that relevant knowledge and understanding for intercultural

competence are knowledge and understanding of one's culture, other cultures, specific culture, general culture, socio-linguistic awareness, cultural adaptation process, openness, ethnocentrism, ethno-relativism, culture shock, and reverse culture shock (UNESCO, 2013). Intercultural competence is the recognition of the uniqueness of all cultures and their values. The people who belong to this school of thought tend to promote cultural superiority, discrimination and bias. Hence, youth organisations and Lagos State government need to emulate Europe, Singapore, China, USA and the Arab World and place priority on intercultural education and competence at all levels of their learning institutions and organisational platforms.

However, from the ANOVA test, the respondents' distribution revealed a significant effect of gender on the level of awareness of intercultural competence amongst youths in Lagos State. Several findings have been conducted on the effect of gender on intercultural competence from different parts of the world. Some scholars used the Intercultural Effectiveness Scale (IES) to examine intercultural competence among foreign students. From their findings, the female students had a high level of understanding of cultural differences, compared to male students in intercultural interactions (Nicolai and Daniel, 2017). The implication is that female seems to exhibit some of the components of intercultural competence better than male.

On the contrary, another researcher conducted a research among Indonesian English teachers to ascertain whether gender influences their intercultural competence or not. The researcher used a self-assessment tool and other relevant measuring instruments designed by the Pestalozzi Programme and the Intercultural Cities project of the Council of European Commission and the European Wergeland Centre to assess their attitude, knowledge, and skills which are major components of intercultural competence. The researcher ascertained that there was no significant effect of gender on intercultural competence among the population of the research, the Indonesian English teachers, and equally affirmed that intercultural competence is needed by everybody in this era of globalisation (Idris, 2021).

Above all, there was no mutual agreement among scholars on whether gender affects knowledge of intercultural competence or not for several factors. One of the factors is differences in the location and data used for analysis. However, today's working environment and globalisation experience make intercultural competence an essential part of every human's life. It then means the knowledge of intercultural competence does not exempt anyone regardless of gender to survive in a multicultural situation. This is also open to further research in the society.

Conclusion

The reality of cultural diversity and intercultural relations in contemporary times has made intercultural competence an indispensable skill to operate in a culturally diverse location effectively and appropriately. As a result, leadership formation and development should be all-encompassing for emerging youth leaders in Lagos State and Nigeria as a whole.

Recommendations

Recommendations for the Government

Since Lagos State is an assemblage of diverse cultural and ethnic nationalities, government should make sure that all its policies recognise the worth of every culture and groups within the state more than ever before.

Recommendations for the Youth Organisations

The leadership of various youth organisations in Lagos State should review their organisational leadership development scheme to recognise the differences in cultural background and social orientations of individuals within their organisations. Apart from common knowledge of leadership, youth organisations should adopt an intercultural approach to foster the leadership development of their members.

Recommendations for the Public and Private Sectors

Lagos State workforce and working environment comprise people from diverse cultural identities and ethnic nationalities. Hence, public and private sectors should create a working relationship that will harmonise individual cultural, social and tribal identities.

Recommendations for Lagos State Inhabitants

Peaceful coexistence is a function of many factors, more importantly in a multicultural state like Lagos. The reality of cultural diversity, workforce and working environment of Lagos State requires every inhabitant to develop intercultural competence. This involves openness, empathy, respect, tolerance, interest in other cultures, and knowledge and understanding of other cultures.

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